

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Rices with multiple disease resistance

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In 1983 kharif, under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, 328 rice cultures of National Screening Nursery I were evaluated at RARS for resistance to blast (BL), sheath blight (ShB), and bacterial blight (BB). B1 screening was done under upland condi-

tions using the uniform B1 nursery pattern. Screening for ShB and BB was in transplanted fields with artificially induced disease. Each test entry was planted in two 2-m rows spaced at 20 × 15 cm for ShB and BB in 2 separate plots. Disease reactions were judged using the *Standard evaluation system for rice scale*.

Sixteen entries were resistant to both B1 and ShB, 6 entries to B1 and BB, and 39 entries to ShB and BB. Four entries had resistance to the three diseases (see table). □

Rices with multiple resistance to B1, ShB, and BB, RARS, Pattambi, India.

IET no.	Cross	Reaction ^a to		
		BL	ShB	BB
8236	CR-151-79/CR1014	MR	MR	R
8288	Vikram/Benong III	MR	MR	MR
8314	IR32/IET6314	MR	MR	MR
8748	Jaya/T22A	R	R	MR

^a MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant.

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INSECT RESISTANCE

Virulence of green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* colonies on rice cultivars with the *Glh 2* or *Glh 5* gene for resistance

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We have unsuccessfully attempted to select GLH colonies that are virulent on ASD7 (which has the *Glh 2* gene for resistance) and on ASD8 (with *Glh 5*). We sought to determine whether other colonies selected for 37 generations for

virulence to Pankhari 203 (*Glh 1*), IR8 (*Glh 3*), Ptb 8 (*glh 4*), TAPL #796 (*Glh 6*), and Moddai Karuppan (*Glh 7*) had cross virulence to ASD7 or ASD8.

Results were compared with colonies reared on susceptible TN1. Resistance scoring was based on population growth.

Six-day-old seedlings of the test cultivars were transplanted, 5 seedlings/pot, in 10-cm-diam clay pots. There were four replications, with each pot representing a replication. Two weeks after transplanting, the individual pots were placed

in 10- × 90-cm mylar film cages to protect them from other pests, parasites, and predators. Ten days later, they were inspected and all parasites, predators, and other pests were removed from the cage. Then, 5 pair (male and female) of GLH adults from the different colonies were introduced into each cage. Twenty-five days after infestation, the GLH population in each cage was counted and progeny per female was calculated.

There were significant differences in the levels of resistance among the seven

Population growth of GLH on different rice cultivars, IRRI.

Cultivar	Gene	Population growth (progeny/female) on each colony ^a					
		Pankhari 203	IR8	Ptb 8	TAPL 796	Moddai Karuppan	TN1
ASD7	<i>Glh 2</i>	1 a (a)	1 a (a)	1 a (a)	1 a (a)	1 a (a)	4 a (a)
Godalki	<i>Glh 2</i>	120 d(a)	55 c (a)	76 d (a)	84 d (a)	68 de (a)	82 d (a)
Lien-tsan 50	<i>Glh 2</i>	27 cd (c)	3 a (a)	4 b (a)	8 bcd (ab)	11 c (ab)	19 b (bc)
Palasithari 601	<i>Glh 2</i>	7 c (a)	3 a (a)	10 bc (a)	2 bc (a)	11 cd (a)	9 ab (a)
Ernest	<i>Glh 2</i>	10 c (ab)	1 a (a)	10 bc (b)	5 bcd (ab)	5 b (ab)	19 b (b)
Bignou	<i>Glh 2</i>	33 cd (b)	14 ab (ab)	16 bc (ab)	11 cd (a)	32 cde (b)	26 bc (ab)
Tilockkachari	<i>Glh 2</i>	1 b (a)	1 a (a)	1 a (a)	2 b (a)	1 a (a)	3 a (a)
ASD8	<i>Glh 5</i>	4 c (ab)	1 a (a)	3 b (a)	1 a (a)	2 ab (a)	20 b (b)
IR29 (resistant check)	Unidentified	23 cd (ab)	22 bc (ab)	25 cd (ab)	3 b (a)	75 de (c)	51 cd (b)
TN1 (susceptible check)	None	134 d (a)	75 d (a)	76 d (a)	97 d (a)	135 e (a)	63 d (a)

^aAv of 4 replications in a column or in a row (in parentheses), means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.